

A Benchmark for Early Time-Series Classification

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Abstract

The objective of Early Time-Series Classification (ETSC) is to predict the class of incoming time-series by observing the fewest time-points possible. Although many approaches have been proposed in the past, not all techniques are suitable for every problem type. In particular, the characteristics of the input data may impact performance. To aid researchers and developers with deciding which kind of method suits their needs best, we developed a framework that allows the comparison of five existing ETSC algorithms, and also introduce a new method that is based on the selective truncation of time-series principle. To promote results reproducibility and the alignment of algorithm comparisons, we also include a bundle of datasets originating from real-world time-critical applications, and for which the application of ETSC algorithms can be considered quite valuable.

2012 ACM Subject Classification Computing methodologies → Machine learning algorithms

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Supplementary Material *Software*: <https://github.com/xarakas/ETSC>

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1 Extended Abstract

Latest technological advancements drive the generation of large volumes of time-series data. Sea vessels, for example, utilize integrated sensory and telecommunication devices to continuously report trajectory information in the form of time-series data. This abundance of data is leveraged by machine learning techniques to address various problems. In the life sciences domain, simulators are incorporated to test the effectiveness of new experimental drugs “in-silico”. Such simulations often require long time and large amounts of computational resources, which, in the case of unsuccessful drug treatment cases being simulated, are consumed in vain [1]. It would be desirable to be able to predict such outcomes early on by observing the simulations course as time-series, and to terminate not interesting trials so to speed up the whole drug discovery process. To this end, the domain of Early Time-Series Classification (ETSC) has an objective to classify time-series at the earliest point possible, before the entire series is observed [5].

Meanwhile, despite the numerous proposed methods for ETSC, there is a notable absence of a dedicated experimental evaluation and comparison framework in this field. Furthermore, ETSC methods are predominantly evaluated and compared against only a limited set of alternative algorithms. In order to fill this gap, we have developed a framework that allows

43 to empirically compare five existing approaches as well as a newly introduced one, using
 44 a curated bundle of datasets from real-world applications. This framework is utilized to
 45 highlight the ETSC algorithms merits and shortcomings when applied to cases with different
 46 features, e.g. dataset size, observation variability, class imbalance, etc. The framework can
 47 be easily extended to include more datasets and algorithms, and is openly available online [2].

48 **Evaluation metrics:** In the ETSC domain, apart from the predictive performance
 49 (accuracy and F_1 -score), there is also the objective to optimize the earliness of the generated
 50 predictions. These two metrics can also be combined into a single metric as a harmonic
 51 mean [9]. Training and testing times are also of interest to consider in real-world applications.

52 **Algorithms:** Our framework includes five existing ETSC algorithms, i.e. *ECEC* [7],
 53 *ECONOMY-K* [3], *ECTS* [10], *EDSC* [11], and *TEASER* [9]. *ECEC* calculates confidence
 54 thresholds above which a class label prediction is considered to be reliable. *ECONOMY-K*
 55 performs clustering on the training data, and estimates the cost of having to observe more
 56 time points to generate a prediction. *ECTS* utilizes nearest neighbors and reverse nearest
 57 neighbors sets for its decisions. *EDSC* extracts shapelets of the training data that are then
 58 matched with the input test data. *TEASER* trains classifiers on overlapping prefixes of the
 59 training data, and then applies an one-class SVM that validates the class label prediction.

60 In addition, we propose a new method that can be configured to utilize different state-of-
 61 the-art full time-series classification algorithms for ETSC. It relies on iteratively truncating
 62 time-series into prefixes of gradually increasing length and then applying *Minirocket* [4],
 63 *MLSTM* [6], and *WEASEL* [8] to the truncated examples for predicting the corresponding
 64 class labels. Thus, for each dataset, a fixed earliness is determined throughout the training
 65 phase. Although this might be suboptimal in the sense that for particular instances the
 66 prediction could have been generated earlier than for others, it constitutes a comprehensive
 67 baseline for diagnosing if applying ETSC to particular datasets and domains would be
 68 successful, i.e. if accurate predictions can be generated earlier, before the whole time-series
 69 is observed. Our approach can incorporate any full time-series classification algorithm.

70 **Datasets:** We have collected 10 publicly available datasets from the UEA & UCR
 71 Time-series Classification Repository, and also introduced two new cases, one originating
 72 from the drug discovery domain, and the other from the field of maritime intelligence. In
 73 turn, these datasets are categorized according to particular characteristics: size, coefficient of
 74 variability, levels of class imbalance, number of distinct class labels, and number of variables.

75 **Comparison results:** Judging by our experimental results, we can see that *ECEC*
 76 achieves the most accurate and early predictions for datasets with lengthy time-series, but
 77 it requires higher training times. When the number of examples in the dataset increases,
 78 the *MLSTM* variant of our method competes with *ECEC* and *TEASER* in terms of the
 79 harmonic mean between accuracy and earliness, but it has higher training times compared
 80 to both. In applications with high variance in measurements and high class imbalance,
 81 *ECEC* and *MLSTM* achieve the highest harmonic mean scores. In multi-class classification
 82 cases, *MLSTM* is the best choice with the lowest earliness scores, followed by *Minirocket*,
 83 which has high accuracy and reduced training times. For the rest of the datasets we tested,
 84 *Minirocket* is the most suitable algorithm for ETSC in terms of harmonic mean. It has very
 85 low earliness scores and training times, although its predictive accuracy is worse than *ECEC*,
 86 *ECONOMY-K*, and *ECTS*, which however achieve higher earliness scores.

87 As concerns future work, we are already in the process of further enriching our framework
 88 with additional ETSC algorithms and more datasets. We believe that establishing consolidated
 89 benchmarking procedures will be of great benefit for the ETSC community.

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